

Research

Comparison of Nephron-Sparing Surgery versus Radical Nephrectomy in patients with pT_{1b} renal cell carcinoma: A meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials

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Abstract : Objective: The purpose of this study was to analyze Articles of nephron sparing surgery (NSS) to radical nephrectomy (RN) for Localized Renal Cell Carcinoma (RCC), of two different surgical by means of the method of meta analysis, in order to provide evidence for clinical treatment of Localized Renal Cell Carcinoma. Methods: Articles including randomized controlled trials (RCTs) studies around the world about nephron sparing surgery (NSS) to radical nephrectomy (RN) for Localized Renal Cell Carcinoma (RCC), were searched by Pubmed, Ovid, CENTRAL(CochraneLibrary), EMBASE, EI, CBMdisc, VIP, WanFangData; studies were chosen at last for Meta-analysis. Results: In accordance with the inclusion criteria selected There were 16 RCTs studies of (NSS) versus RN for RCC included in this Meta-analysis. A total of 20972 patients from 16 studies were included, of which NSS group of 4952 and a RN group of 16020. After 3 years of cancer specific mortality relative risk (RR) RR=0.88, 95%CI [0.70 1.12], P=0.30; after 5 years of cancer specific mortality relative risk (RR) RR=1.07, 95%CI [0.75 1.51], P=0.71; After 7 years of cancer specific mortality relative risk (RR) RR=0.88, 95%CI [0.77 1.01], P=0.07; the postoperative recurrence of tumor is the relative risk (RR) RR=1.03, 95%CI [0.69 1.55], P=0.88; postoperative tumor metastasis comparison of relative risk was (RR) RR=0.99, 95%CI [0.77 1.27], P=0.92; the occurrence of postoperative bleeding is the relative risk (RR) RR=1.58, 95%CI [1.03 2.42], P=0.04; There were statistical significance; the occurrence of postoperative renal failure cases compared to the relative risk (RR) RR=0.97, 95%CI [0.68 1.41], P=0.89; the occurrence of postoperative mortality compared to the relative risk (RR) RR=0.92, 95%CI [0.68 1.23], P=0.56. Conclusions: There is no significant differences between NSS and RN with regard to five year cancer related mortality. Tumor recurrence and metastasis. NSS could maximally preserve the function of the remaining nephron and reduce the risk for kidney function failure. Although RN is superior in the prevention of prospective complications, NSS is an effective and reliable treatment for localized renal cell carcinoma.

Keywords: nephron-sparing surgery ; radical nephrectomy ; T_{1b} renal cell carcinoma; Meta-analysis; randomized control test;

For many years RN has been the gold standard for the treatment of T_{1b} stage kidney cancer.¹⁷ However, with the development of kidney imaging and advances of surgical techniques, more and more sporadic tumors without clinical symptoms, localized early tumors and small tumors were found. Continuing to follow the routine RN treatment is bound to be flawed with rigorous treatment. As NSS can ensure good tumor-free patient survival while it maximally preserves remnant kidney nephron and residual renal function, it has received more and more attention from clinicians. However, because the lack of large-scale controlled clinical studies, considerable controversy exist as to whether the nephron-sparing surgical treatment should be chosen for the T_{1b} patients of renal cell carcinoma with completely normal contra-lateral kidney function. Therefore, we used Meta-analysis to compare the efficacy of NSS and RN treatments on T_{1b} kidney cancer patients, so that we are aware of the postoperative conditions following the two surgical procedures, such as survival, recurrence rate, tumor metastasis and surgical complications. Subsequently, we can provide evidence-based medical proof for selection of clinical surgical treatment strategies.

Materials and Methods

Data sources and selection

We searched Medline, EMBase, and EI, VIP database, Articles Digital Periodicals published domestically and abroad for the literature regarding the efficacy and safety of NSS and RN treatments on localized kidney cancer patients. The combinations of the following search terms were chosen: “nephron-sparing surgery”、 “radical nephrectomy”、 “T_{1b} renal cell carcinoma”、 “Meta-analysis”and “randomised control test”.

Literature inclusion criteria: ① Types of study: comparative clinical trials on NSS and RN for the treatment of T_{1b} stage kidney cancer, either open surgery or laparoscopy minimal invasive surgery, randomization or blinding method was used. ② Types of cases: T_{1b} patients of renal cell tumors with normal contralateral renal function, single tumors, unilateral tumors; while patients with solitary kidney, distant lymph node tumor metastasis and previous medical history of nephrectomy and other tumors were excluded. ③ Endpoint types: tumor recurrence, metastasis, and rates of surgical complication within maximal follow-up period. Abstracts were read, and full text documents meet the inclusion criteria thereby were then been selected for inclusion. Related reviews were read to supplement the test data that was not retrieved by initial searches. After the data were confirmed, relevant data were extracted for Meta-analysis.

Statistical methods

Rev Man5.2 software was used for Meta-analysis. The numerical data were statistically analyzed using relative risk (RR) and 95% CI as the efficacy analytical statistic, $P \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Statistical heterogeneity among the included study results was tested using the X^2 test, with the test level of $\alpha = 0.1$. Meanwhile, the heterogeneity was quantitatively detected by I^2 . When $P \geq 0.1$ and $I^2 \leq 50\%$, the statistical heterogeneity of the results among studies was considered relatively big, and the cause of heterogeneity was further analyzed. When there is no significant clinical heterogeneity, meta-analysis of a random effect model was applied. Otherwise, descriptive analysis was applied. When necessary, sensitivity analysis was used to test the stability of the results.

Results

According the inclusion criteria of the current meta-analysis to select comparative RCT studies regarding the treatment efficacy of NSS and RN on RCC, a total of 16 articles¹⁻¹⁶ (Fig 1)and 20,972 cases were included, of which 4,952 and 16,020 cases belong to the NSS and RN group, respectively.

FIG.1. Flowchart of the screening process.

2.1 Meta-analysis of the 3-year overall survival rate after RSS and RN surgical treatment of T_{1b} stage kidney cancer

A total of 9 articles and 11,205 patients were included (see Figure 2.1 for details). Heterogeneity test $P = 0.96$, homogeneity between studies was relatively good. A fixed effect model was combined for Meta-analysis. The results show: The 3-year survival rates of the nephron-sparing surgery group and the radical nephrectomy were 3% (109/3516) and 3% (245/7689), respectively. The OR value was 0.88, 95% CI [0.70, 1.12], $P = 0.3$. The difference was considered not statistically significant.

Figure 2.1 Forest plot on the meta-analysis results of the 3-year cancer-specific mortality following the two surgical methods

Figure 2.1.1 Funnel plot on the meta-analysis results of the 3-year cancer-specific mortality following the two surgical methods

2.2 Meta-analysis of the 5-year overall survival rate after RSS and RN surgical treatment of T_{1b} stage kidney cancer

A total of 5 articles and 2,277 patients were included (see Figure 2.2 for details). Heterogeneity test $P = 0.85$, homogeneity between studies was relatively good. A fixed effect model was combined for Meta-analysis. The results show: the 5-year survival rates of the nephron-sparing surgery group and the radical nephrectomy were 7% (56/794) and 6% (94/1483), respectively. The OR value was 1.07, 95% CI [0.75, 1.51], $P = 0.3$. The difference was considered not statistically significant.

Figure 2.2 Forest plot on the meta-analysis results of the 5-year cancer-specific mortality following the two surgical methods

Figure 2.2.1 Funnel plot on the meta-analysis results of the 5-year cancer-specific mortality following the two surgical methods

2.3 Meta-analysis of the 7-year overall survival rate after RSS and RN surgical treatment of T_{1b} stage kidney cancer

A total of 10 articles and 11,261 patients were included (see Figure 2.3 for details). Heterogeneity test $P = 0.00001$, there is no heterogeneity among the various groups, and the homogeneity was relatively good. A fixed effect model was combined for Meta-analysis. The results show: the 7-year survival rates of the nephron-sparing surgery group and the radical nephrectomy were 90.0% (3179/3532) and 92.4% (7146/7729), respectively. The OR value was 0.88, 95% CI [0.77, 1.01], $P = 0.07$. The difference was considered not statistically significant.

Figure 2.3 Forest plot on the Meta-analysis results of the 7-year cancer-specific mortality following the two surgical methods

Figure 2.3.1 Funnel plot on the Meta-analysis results of the 7-year cancer-specific mortality following the two surgical methods

2.4 Meta-analysis of the recurrence rate after RSS and RN surgical treatment of T_{1b} stage kidney cancer

A total of 5 articles and 9,327 patients were included (see Figure 2.4 for details). Heterogeneity test $P = 0.98$, the homogeneity among various groups was relatively good. A fixed effect model was combined for Meta-analysis. The results show: the recurrence rates of the nephron-sparing surgery group and the radical nephrectomy were 2% (33/1373) and 2% (182/7954), respectively. The OR value was 1.03, 95% CI [0.69, 1.55], $P = 0.88$. The difference was considered not statistically significant.

Figure 2.4 Forest plot on the Meta-analysis results of the recurrence rate following the two surgical methods

Figure 2.4.1 Funnel plot on the Meta-analysis results of the recurrence rate following the two surgical methods

2.5 Meta-analysis of tumor metastasis after RSS and RN surgical treatment of T_{1b} stage kidney cancer

A total of 6 articles and 5,246 patients were included (see Figure 2.5 for details). Heterogeneity test $P = 0.98$, the homogeneity among various groups was relatively good. A fixed effect model was combined for Meta-analysis. The results show: the metastasis rates following the nephron-sparing surgery group and the radical nephrectomy were 6.7% (88/1297) and 7.2% (288/3949), respectively. The OR value was 0.99, 95% CI [0.77, 1.27], $P = 0.92$. The difference was considered not statistically significant.

Figure 2.5 Forest plot on the Meta-analysis results of the metastasis rate following the two surgical methods

Figure 2.5.1 Funnel plot on the Meta-analysis results of the metastasis rate following the two surgical methods

2.6 Meta-analysis of bleeding comparison following RSS and RN surgical treatment of T_{1b} stage kidney cancer

A total of 6 articles and 16,592 patients were included (see Figure 2.6 for details). Heterogeneity test $P = 0.01$, the homogeneity among various groups was relatively good. A fixed effect model was combined for Meta-analysis. The results show: the rates of bleeding following the nephron-sparing surgery group and the radical nephrectomy were 5.7% (186/3226) and 4.6% (616/13366), respectively. The OR value was 1.58, 95% CI [1.03, 2.42], $P = 0.04$. The difference was considered statistically significant.

Figure 2.6 Forest plot on the Meta-analysis results of bleeding comparison following the two surgical methods

Figure 2.6.1 Funnel plot on the Meta-analysis results of bleeding comparison following the two surgical methods

2.7 Meta-analysis of renal failure comparison following RSS and RN surgical treatment of T_{1b} stage kidney cancer

A total of 10 articles and 18,012 patients were included (see Figure 2.7 for details). Heterogeneity test $P = 0.0007$, the homogeneity among various groups was relatively good. A fixed effect model was combined for Meta-analysis. The results show: the rates of renal failure following the nephron-sparing surgery group and the radical nephrectomy were 5.5% (216/3912) and 4.6% (649/14100), respectively. The OR value was 0.97, 95% CI [0.68, 1.41], $P = 0.89$. The difference was considered not statistically significant.

Figure 2.7 Forest plot on the Meta-analysis results of renal failure comparison following the two surgical methods

Figure 2.7.1 Funnel plot on the Meta-analysis results of renal failure comparison following the two surgical methods

2.8 Analysis of bias

Funnel plot of RevMan 5.2 software was used to measure the included studies. The graphic of the variables was basically symmetry, with all points mostly concentrated in the middle of the funnel. However, because the included articles were all published literature, a publication bias is unavoidable.

3. Discussion

In 1969 Robson et al. established RN as a standard treatment for T_{1b} stage renal cell carcinoma, and used the standard surgical treatment for kidney cancer. With this surgery, survival rate of kidney cancer patients has improved, and recurrence and metastasis rate has been very low. In the past few decades, RN has been probably the preferred treatment choice for curing of T_{1b} the stage kidney cancer.¹⁸ However, the complete removal of the entire kidney of the patients during the RN procedure resulted in a sharp reduction of nephrons. Consequently, the residual contralateral nephrons are encountered with high pressure, high perfusion, high filtration compensatory hemodynamic changes, leading to proteinuria, hypertension, and even risk of renal failure with the residual renal units.

RCT study is the ideal object of meta-analysis, yet a completely randomly controlled study in the surgical treatment of renal cell carcinoma is still extremely difficult to achieve. At present relevant research results is relatively scarce. Meta-analysis of RCT has only been conducted on a few studies of NSS and RN. On the included RCT studies, we evaluated the treatment efficacy and safety in terms of postoperative tumor-specific mortality and postoperative recurrence, metastasis, etc. However, the included articles in our analysis have the limitations of an early time frame, a relatively small patient number and fairly less data for extraction. The Meta-analysis included a total of 16 studies, which is a small number of articles that were properly

randomized as mentioned. Nevertheless, probably because of the characteristics in surgeries of kidney cell carcinoma, none of the included studies used double-blind method. Four research articles are of low inclusion quality because they did not mention the issues of exit and lost to follow up. The remaining 12 articles are scored of 3 points and are of good quality as included studies. Like the meta-analysis of currently existing RCT, the extracted variables in our studies, except for the postoperative complications, showed significant heterogeneity problem. Thus the quality of the included studies are not of high quality literature. Among the 16 included studies in the literature, some studies have not described in detail the method of randomization, and neither described the concealment of the randomized allocation program. These are factors that could lead to the selective test bias. Thus, we did not perform one by one meta-regression analysis on the variables for the common heterogeneity of the external characteristics (publication time of the articles, type of study, number of cases, the patient's stage of disease) of the literature. Thus, elimination of the above confounding factors of heterogeneity could not reduce the heterogeneity of the results, hence we did not perform subgroup analysis on the mentioned articles. This study only included correlation analysis of relevant literature, and all included studies are of foreign literature, while domestic literature was excluded, there may be significant publication bias. In particular, the bias may significantly limit the promotion and practicality of the research results in clinical use.

Currently the use of NSS in clinical treatment of T_{1b} stage kidney cancer is still controversial. Firstly, comparing with RN, for the lack of large-scale and formal multi-center randomized and controlled trials, the postoperative clinical efficacy of NSS in treatment of kidney cancer has not been confirmed. Whether not removing the diseased kidney in NSS will cause postoperative renal tumor recurrence and metastasis is rather concerned by many physicians and patients. In our systematic review of the literature data that meet the requirements, the 5-year postoperative survival, recurrence and metastasis of kidney cancer patients treated by NSS and RN were not statistically significant, indicating that the clinical efficacy of NSS and RN is similar. The risk of postoperative tumor recurrence and metastasis of the kidney cancer patients did not increase because of NSS surgery. In addition, in clinical work, NSS can cause more postoperative complications because of its relatively high difficulty, longer operative time, large tissue trauma, and high requirement on the surgeon and the surgical equipment conditions. These issues limit the application of NSS in the treatment of localized kidney cancer.

In this systematic evaluation we have compared NSS and RN on the total incidence of complications after surgery. The results show that RN is better than NSS in prevention and reduction of the overall incidence of postoperative complications. However, the results also show that NSS is significantly superior to RN in the prevention and treatment of postoperative renal failure, which is dependent on the reservation of residual nephrons and protection of the residual renal functions after NSS operation. These advantages of NSS are beneficial for improving the postoperative life and treatment, and prolong postoperative survival time of kidney cancer patients. With the promotion and popularization of NSS in clinical use, enrichment of the surgeons' experience and improvement of surgical instruments, the postoperative complications of NSS are expected to gradually decrease.

In summary, through this initial clear T_{1b} Meta-analysis of patients with renal cell carcinoma line NSS RN curative effect is similar, although the NSS and more complications than the RN, but because it maximize the retention of patients with renal units to protect residual renal function, reduce postoperative renal failure risk, so NSS for T_{1b} renal cancer patients is still a valid and reliable operation, it is worth to promote in clinical practice, with large-scale

randomized clinical controlled experimental study of standardized emergence, as more statistically accurate and significant results will be obtained for excellent clinical outcomes .

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